

around 1370 kilometers. Yamuna originates from the Yamunotri Glacier. River Tons and Giri are the important tributaries of Yamuna and principle source of water in mountainous ranges. Yamuna flows through the states of Delhi, Haryana and Uttar Pradesh, before merging with the Ganges at Allahabad.

On the basis of hydrological and ecological conditions Yamuna has been classified into five segments that are Himalayan Segment, Upper Segment, Delhi Segment, Eutrophicated Segment and Diluted Segment as shown in Figure 1 (CWC, 2009).

Delhi is the major contributor of pollution for Yamuna followed by Agra (9%) and then Mathura. The condition of river deteriorates further due to abstraction of significant amount of river water, leaving almost no fresh water in the river, which is essential to maintain the assimilation capacity of the river. The Yamuna is widely worshipped by devotees in India. A few centuries ago, it prompted the Mughals to build one of their most magnificent monuments; the Taj Mahal on its bank; but today it has been reduced to a pale and stinking drain. The version of the river that we see in Agra today is Agra canal.

STUDY AREA

The present study has been focused on the Yamuna River in Agra. For the present study river water samples & soil samples testing along with surveying was done along the stretch of Yamuna from Poiya Ghat where the river enters the city to behind the Taj Mahal (the river leaves the city in proximity from this point). The average area of the city is 188.40 km². The population of the city is around 1,746,467 (2011). It has a semi-arid climate. The soil is generally loose and sandy.

OBJECTIVES

The present study tries to find out the:

1. Role of the city in polluting Yamuna
2. Effect of toxicity on vegetables farming on riverbanks
3. Utilization & effect of river water on life forms
4. Conservatory methods applied if any

METHODOLOGY

We took water and soil samples from Poiya Ghat, Hatti Ghat and Taj Ganj to be tested in laboratory to find out the presence of various heavy metals and chemicals (Fig 2). Questionnaire was prepared and random sampling & surveying was done to find out the

utilization of river water by people. Visits to various government offices provided the authors with the application of conservatory methods. Help form secondary sources were also taken.

Figure 2: The sampling sites along with the areas of highest concentration of industries (Courtesy: Google Earth)

DISCUSSION

Agra is a major contributor of pollution to the river Yamuna. It comes second after Delhi in polluting Yamuna. According to the Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB) the water quality of Yamuna River falls under the category “E” which makes it fit only for recreation and industrial cooling, completely ruling out the possibility for underwater life (www.hinduonnet.com). As per data on water quality of water bodies and groundwater locations; it was placed seventh on the list of rivers with highest Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD), one of the most important indicators of pollution. BOD level in Agra stretch of Yamuna was found at 34 mg/l while the COD level was at 64 mg/l (CPCB, 2006). The permissible level is 3 mg/L (Misra, 2010). Agra downstream shows the presence of Cadmium, Nickel, Iron, Zinc and Chromium in Yamuna River.

ROLE OF THE CITY IN POLLUTING YAMUNA

Yamuna enters the city at Poiya Ghat. From this point itself the city along with its urban counterpart starts polluting the river water. When the authors visited the survey sites we found pollution in the form of

1. Agricultural pollution sources
2. Dumping of garbage and dead bodies

3. Immersion of idols
4. Pollution due to in-stream uses of water

Although we didn't see any direct pollution of river water on agriculture, but the slope of the land suggests that during rainy season, the runoff invariably carries with it pesticides, insecticides, chemical fertilizers etc used by the farmers in the fields. These accumulate in the river water. Some of these get mixed with the water and flow further downstream while some may lodge itself in the sandy bed. Further the chemical pesticides, insecticides and fertilizers used in the flood plains during non-monsoon season easily get mixed with the river water when these lands get covered with water during monsoons.

As per the report of the Yamuna Action Plan the content of suspended solids in Yamuna is 1000-10,000 mg/L and the permissible content of suspended solids is 100 mg/L (Misra, 2012). We witnessed numerous live incidences of garbage dumping in the river. These ranged from flowers, eatables, kitchen waste, unknown wastes wrapped in big jute bags etc. Majority of the garbage were packed in plastics. Thus, these are doubly harmful. In our survey we could also witness 1 case of human semi burned dead body floating in the river.

Immersion of idols in the river during the festival season has become a cause for concern because of increased use of cheap lead and chrome-based paints in most of them. Increased use of plaster of Paris is not only affecting the humans and animals dependent on them but is also deteriorating the ecological condition of the river. During the immersion ceremony, puja articles such as polythene bags, foam cut-outs, flowers, food offerings, decorations, metal polish, plastic sheets, cosmetic items, all of which are highly polluting, are also thrown into the water (Kaur *et al*, 2013).

Bathing of cattle, though not very common however, is being done. Some cases of human bathing were also noted. Early morning riverbanks become a public open defecation area. The degradable pollutants use up the available oxygen in the water, thereby reducing the oxygen content of the water. Further the non-degradable and the toxic chemicals mixes with the water.

Majority of the sewerage canals drain itself out into the Yamuna at this point. There are a number of *Dhobi Ghat* also available in this area. The untreated sewerage along with night soil easily finds its way into the "Holy" Yamuna. At last, having received her share of pollution from Agra, Yamuna finally leaves the city in Taj Ganj area (near the Taj Mahal). Apart from

household sewerage industrial untreated or semi treated toxic sewerage water also is dumped into the river at various locations. The result of the test is as below:

S. No.	Parameters	Poiya Ghat	Hathi Ghat	Taj Gang
1.	TDS	720	755	785
2.	EC	1115	1210	1150
3.	Turbidity	14.5	13.1	30.2
4.	pH	7.2	7.4	7.5

EFFECT OF TOXICITY ON VEGETABLES FARMING ON RIVERBANKS

The flow of river water except during monsoons is very low. However, during the monsoons, the rain in the upstream along with release of water by the various barrages, obstructing the flow of the river water, causes the flow volume to increase considerably. This causes flooding in the flood plains. As a result, the toxic elements present in the river water now accumulate in the vegetables being grown in the flood plains. Sometimes temporary agriculture (during non-monsoon season) is done just on the banks of the river during which water is directly hauled from the river by pipe. A study of the soil samples from agricultural fields on the Yamuna flood plains at distance of around 100-150 mts were done to study the contamination levels in the flood bank. Chromium ranged from 11.22 mg/Kg to 18.29 mg/Kg. Level of around 22-25 mg/kg has an adverse effect on human health. Mercury ranged between 0.46 mg/Kg to 45.26 mg/kg much higher than the limit of 1 mg/kg. Lead levels ranged from below detection to 40 times over the permissible limits (Misra, 2010). The vegetables growing in this soil absorb the contaminants. Leafy vegetables are high accumulators of heavy metals. These vegetables become the carriers of heavy metals in our food chain.

UTILIZATION & EFFECT OF RIVER WATER ON LIFE FORMS

Effect on humans

In our survey of 50 people, we found 02 people using the water directly. There was 00 case of bathing, 00 case of drinking. Except those fields which are situated on the banks of the river almost all the farmers use underground water using submersibles for irrigation. A general awareness against the direct use of water was seen. Of the 50 people sampled 3 septuagenarians could recall direct usage/consumption of river water around 15-20 years back. This clearly

points out the fact that Yamuna has been rendered useless for direct consumption owing to pollution since 15-20 years. Those who are using the water directly at present are doing so owing to helpless economic situation. Skin rashes, infection and stomach ailments were reported by them.

However though not directly, indirectly toxic elements are entering into the human food chain through vegetables. Heavy metals have been shown to mainly enter the human body through food and water and are known to have serious health implications (Schwartz, 1994). Table 1 is a summary of the various heavy metals detected in the environment and their effect on human health.

Table 1: Heavy metals and their effect on human health

S.No	Pollutants	Major Sources	Effect on Human
1	Lead	Paint, Pesticide, Batteries, Crystal Glass Preparation.	Cognitive Impairment in Children, Peripheral Neuropathy in Adults, Developmental Delay
2	Copper	Electroplating, Pesticide Production, Mining.	Headache, Nausea, Vomiting Diarrhea and Kidney Malfunctioning
3	Zinc	Effluents From Electroplating Industries, Sewage Discharge, The Immersion Of Painted Idols	Vomiting, Diarrhea, Icterus, Liver and Kidney Damage
4	Nickel	Stainless Steel Manufacturing Units, Electroplating Factory Discharge	Neurotoxic, Genotoxic, & Carcinogenic Agent, Nickel Dermatitis
5	Cadmium	Electroplating, Preparation of Cd-Ni Batteries, Control Rods, Shields within Nuclear Reactors, Television Phosphors.	Kidney And Liver Damage. Renal Dysfunction, Gastrointestinal Damage

Source: Malik et. al., 2014

The effluents from the various industries are discharged into the Yamuna adding a variety of the above-mentioned heavy metals. These in turn enters human body through food chain in one form or other.

Effect on aquatic life

The fact that Yamuna is a toxic river has been proved in the earlier discussions. It is thus quite natural that the primary blunt of her toxicity will be faced by the aquatic life- especially fishes. The various industrial outlets which drain into the river is a probable source of the heavy metals in the Yamuna, leading to severe effects in humans, fish, and plants.

In a study for determination of heavy metals in fish species characterization of heavy metals in fish elucidated that the concentrations of Ca, K, Mg, Na and P were too high as compared with other metal and were not in the maximum permissible level set by World Health Organization (WHO). (Sen *et al*, 2011). The river dolphin has disappeared from the Yamuna. The flow prior to Delhi has a water depth of about 0.6 m through the peak summer months, which is too meagre to support a healthy fish population.

In recent years Yamuna River is proving to be the death bed of numerous aquatic life specially fishes. Almost every year large scale fish death is being reported. On 26th June 2014 hundreds of dead fishes were found floating at Samgor ghat of river Yamuna in Etmadpur area of Agra. On 13th June 2002, thousands of dead and dying fishes were found strewn over the Sikandra Taj Mahal area along the water body. Reports of more fish deaths poured in from Bateshwar, about 78 km from Poiya Ghat in Agra (Fig 3) (Verma, 2002). The fishermen community of Agra in general replied in the negative when asked whether they get their maximum haul from Yamuna adding that haulage has drastically decreased in the recent years.

Figure 3: Variation in the availability of fishes during last 15 years

According to the survey among fisher men community, the species of fishes available 10-15 years ago were Tingra, Ritha, Baam, Mangor, Rohu & Kroti. Mangor which is the most caught now days, can survive in dirty water. However, Sol which can survive in dirty water,

isn't available. Apart from this Talapiya, Lachi and Chena are also available but in low quantity.

Haulage increases downstream after Bateshwar. Major reason according to the local people is the large number of poly bags in this region which impede the growth here.

Figure 4: Area of large-scale fish death

CONSERVATORY METHODS APPLIED IF ANY

Yamuna Action Plan (YAP) had been started in 1993. Over 4,439 crore (81.3 million US dollars) have been spent by government bodies of Delhi, Uttar Pradesh, and Haryana to implement the projects of this plan (Mahapatra, 2012). This approach to control pollution and restore the river has proved futile, based both on a review of the Ministry of the Forest and Environment’s most recent YAP Report released in 2002. YAP-II which has been introduced in 2002 seems to run on the same path as YAP. The project addresses the abatement of severe pollution of the river Yamuna by raising sewage treatment capacity, expanding capacity of old sewage treatment plants in Delhi and Agra. Public participation and awareness activities have also been planned in the project.

Time will speak as to the result of YAP-II. However in the meantime we should focus on bottom-up local level grass-root level approach rather than huge scale top down approach. At present there is no visible conservatory approach towards the restoration of the river from the point of view of Agra. However, as a city housing the world-famous heritage monument we should take extra burden for maintaining a sustainable development of Yamuna. Certain grass root methods can be undertaken for checking further pollution of the river.

1. **Keep waste out of waterways:** Almost all the metropolitan cities these days have developed door to door garbage/waste collection systems. This is either done directly by personnel of Municipal Corporation or outsourced to private companies. Agra has hardly this facility. People staying close to river or sewage canals joining the river thus find the easy way of dumping into the river or canals. Proper door to door garbage collection system will surely reduce solid waste disposal into the river

directly or indirectly (through sewerage canals). Further recycling units of solid wastes should be developed.

2. **Conserve water and use it effectively:** during the non-monsoon season the Agra stretch of the river just has 1 ft of water which is also mercilessly hauled. In the absence of canal irrigation agriculture is done through submersibles which is taxing both on the ground water and fuel. At present the city does not have any water conservation technique. If small earthen canals connecting the river can be built, it can serve the dual requirement of fetching the extra water into the fields during the monsoon and act as good recharging zones for groundwater through seepage and infiltration. Further these canals will also act as catchment zones for the water thirsty Yamuna. The excess water which otherwise would have run-off and enhanced soil erosion and subsequent sedimentation in the riverbed can be used profitably through this. The soil type of Agra will enhance easy recharge being loose and sandy. Alluvial areas, riverbeds, areas interlinked with main valley and tributaries are best suited for recharge.
3. **Promote wastewater treatment and technologies:** Wastewater can be categorized as domestic/town and industrial. While treatment of industrial effluent is required, and standards exist, enforcement of industrial pollution control by the State Pollution Control Board appears negligible. Industry appears largely self-policing its waste and pollution. At present there is negligible city/domestic wastewater treatment facility and the water through various canals dump itself directly into the river. The city needs to have proper wastewater treatment facility. In Florida municipal wastewater is treated properly and the same is used for ground water recharge. In countries like Israel, France etc water is recycled and used 3-4 times before being discarded. However, in India we discard single use and virgin water. The wastewater after being recycled and treated can be used by the industries. This will check over haulage of the already depleting Yamuna and check direct addition of toxic elements like ammonia (domestic waste). Similarly, the State Pollution Control Board should regularly check the industrial effluent (and share data with local municipal corporation & public) whether it is under maximum permissible limits.

The city like the rest of the country is undergoing rapid urban sprawl in the fringe area in the form of high-rise apartments. Various municipal corporations (Pune, Chennai, Mumbai, Bangalore, Coimbatore etc) these days has made it mandatory for high rise apartments and individual houses (in some areas) to have water recycling facility, wastewater treatment and roof top rainwater harvesting. It is more than high time for the city to follow suit. This will

decrease over dependence on river water and ground water as well as help reduce toxic elements in wastewater.

4. **Drainage water management and treatment:** different kinds of check dams can be built in the main, sub main or lateral drain. These structures control the surface runoff and ensure the maximum infiltration of drainage water and recharge the water table. Within the drainage canal artificial filters or natural filters can be incorporated (gravels, sponge etc) which can help in filtration of the water before joining the river.

5. **Financing wastewater management schemes:** Nowadays a number of NGO's, environmental agencies, corporate houses etc are working on wastewater treatment and management. They can be encouraged to do so for the city. Further research bodies within the government can be approached for funding of projects based on this purpose.

6. **Upgrading of Sewage treatment plant:** it is most important to upgrade / introduce sewage treatment facility for the city. Without proper treatment the toxic water is getting infiltrated to the sub surface and getting mixed with the river water when it is directly dumped into it.

7. **Awareness among farmers towards agricultural practices:** in their effort to gain more crop yield, farmers tend to add chemical fertilizers, pesticides, and insecticides far more than the prescribed limits. The extra amount never makes it to the plant tissue but end up evaporating, getting washed down to the local waterways, leaching or infiltrating surface or sub surface water reservoirs etc. During rainy season the runoff loaded with chemicals pollute the river. Regular awareness camps should be set up not only by the government officials but also by the intellectual class (university/colleges) to spread awareness against overuse of chemicals in farmlands.

8. **Other methods:** The bank of Yamuna is in dire requirement of Afforestation. This will arrest runoff from agricultural fields, soil erosion, enhance rainfall, and secure biodiversity. From our surveys it was well understood that people are aware of the problem Yamuna is facing. Thus, it may be termed as human callousness that the Yamuna is getting toxic day by day. So, imposition of fines and proper legislation is required to save the river. In certain cases, the local government must take up a strong stand notwithstanding religious sentiments. For example, complete ban on disposal of flowers, eatables (after pooja), wood cremation (electric crematorium is already present in the city) etc.

CONCLUSION

Yamuna is the lifeline of Agra. The fact that we as a city are aiding in its slow death has been proved in the discussions above. It is estimated that the rate at which the river is being

poisoned and it's damming at various places both upstream and downstream of Agra will enhance its death by 2030-2050. If as a city, we can abide by simple grass root level methods and techniques the pollution of Yamuna can be checked to a considerable amount. Further the city can prove to be an example and guiding force of micro level river basin planning for other cities in the Indo-Gangetic plain. Emphasis must be given to the easily feasible and economically feasible techniques capable of removing or minimizing chemicals and toxic elements from wastewater.

It can be concluded by saying that no amount of sustainable development is possible for a populous and intellectually developed country like India except without proper and strong legislation, regular check-up and imposition of fines on the offenders.

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